

Method Development and Validation of a Simultaneous Equation Method for UV Spectroscopy-Based Estimation of Rosuvastatin and Telmisartan in Bulk and Dosage Form

Yamini V, Ranjith Kumar D*

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
PSG college of pharmacy, Coimbatore – 641 044, India,
Affiliated to The TN Dr MGR Medical University Chennai.

Address for correspondence

Ranjith Kumar D

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis

PSG college of pharmacy

Coimbatore – 641 044, Tamil Nadu

ABSTRACT:

Objective: A Straight forward, correct and accurate spectrophotometric technique have been established to estimate rosuvastatin calcium, telmisartan in bulk and dosage form by simultaneous estimation technique.

Method: The solution was prepared by combining the ACN and water in a 70:30 ratio as solvent system Rosuvastatin calcium and telmisartan has a 242nm and 296nm 296nm respectively.

Results and discussion: Both drugs were found to exhibit linearity in the range of concentration of 1-5ug/ml and 4-20ug/ml respectively. percentage purity and recovery analysis was also at the limit of 98-102% in both drugs. limit of detection of these two drugs was found to be 0.508ug/ml and 1.54ug/ml respectively. Limit of Quantitation for rosuvastatin and telmisartan were found to be 1.202µg/ml and 4.06µg/ml respectively. The procedure proves to be accurate, easy and exact and could be utilized to estimate routinely Rosuvastatin and Telmisartan.

Keywords: Rosuvastatin calcium, Telmisartan, uv-visible spectrophotometry, simultaneous estimation method, validation parameter.

INTRODUCTION:

Rosuvastatin and Telmisartan are fixed dose combination of Lipid Lowering agent of Rosuvastatin 10mg and Anti Hypertensive agent of Telmisartan 40 mg. Rosuvastatin is a pharmacologically a lipid lowering agent. It is a competitive inhibitor of HMG-CoA reductase. It also mediates the metabolism of 3-hydroxyl-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A to mevalonate, which is a rate limiting step in the synthesis of cholesterol in the liver. Telmisartan competes with angiotensin II-angiotensin II AT1-receptor binding by pharmacologically interacting with the receptors of the vascular smooth muscle and the adrenal gland in a reversible and selective manner. As angiotensin II is a vasoconstrictor, which also stimulates the synthesis and release of aldosterone, blockage of its effects results in decreases in systemic vascular resistance. Telmisartan is not an angiotensin converting enzyme, other hormone receptor or ion channel inhibitor [1,2,3]. The chemical structure of Rosuvastatin and Telmisartan is shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Recently, there is the use of fixed dosage form of Rosuvastatin calcium and Telmisartan in the treatment of Hyperlipidaemia. These experiments will include the different analysis methods were conducted such as UV spectroscopy, HPLC, HPTLC have been reported to be used with individual drug and in combination with other drugs and has published an article on uv with methanol and phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) in ratio of 30:70 as solvent system to be simultaneously used with various dosage forms.

However, this study uses ACN and Water as solvent instead using buffer. The developed method was simple, sharp, consistent, predictable and it is utterly validated as per ICH guidelines. However current work emphasizes on quantitative estimation of ROS and TEL in bulk and combined tablet dosage form and this was carried out for routine analysis.

Figure 1: Rosuvastatin calcium

Figure 2 :Telmisartan

Materials and Methods:

Apparatus:

Instrument used to analyse both drugs in uv- visible double beam spectrophotometer, SCHIMADZU (model UV-1650), software used here was UV Probe 2.42 with a pair of 1cm pathlength matched quartz cells. Spectral bandwidth about 1nm. Sartorius BSA224S- CW an analytical balance and ultrasonic cleanser model (LMUC9D) were used in this study.

Reagents and Materials :

Pure Active pharmaceutical ingredient of ROS&TEL were procured from repeated pharmaceutical Industry. The marketed formulation was purchased from local market separately under the brand name (**TELROSE[®]**). HPLC water was purchased from Qualigens.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION:

CHOICE OF SOLVENTS:

The analysis used a selection of an appropriate solvent based on the analysis of various mixtures of ACN and water .ACN and water (70:30) mixture was identified as the best mix and was thus chosen.

SELECTION OF WAVELENGTH:

The solvent was a mixture of ACN and water ,which was used to prepare the standard solutions of ROS and TEL .AUV spectrophotometer was used to analyze the solutions in the wavelength of 200-400nm. ACN and water mixture was taken as blank to correct the baseline.The absorbance spectra was measured ,and the corresponding wavelength graphs for both ROSU and TEL were determined.

SPECTROSCOPIC CONDITIONS:

Optimal analytical conditions that were applied when performing the study were the analysis were done using a solvent mixture of ACN and water in a ratio of 70:30. The measurements were done in spectrum mode. The light ranged to scan was 200-400nm.The range of absorbance was kept at 0.0 and 2.0 absorbance .The speed of scan was set at medium.

DETECTION WAVELENGTHS:

Two wavelengths are detected at 242nm which is the maximum wavelength of ROS,296nm which is the maximum wavelength of TEL.

Preparation of stock solution:

1 mg of ROS and 4 mg of TEL was taken and transferred into 25 mL volumetric flask separately and volume was made up to 1 25 mL with ACN and milli Q-distilled water in the ratio (70:30) to dissolve it completely. The final concentration were 100 µg/mL for both drugs.

Selection of wavelength:

The dilutions were made to the concentrations of 10g/ml for rosuvastatin and 10g/ml for fortelmisartan solution. The solutions were scanned in uv 200-400nm against reagent blank.The spectrum study showed Rosuvastatin and

telmisartan shows a well condition max at 242 and 296nm respectively. These wavelength was selected for the development of simultaneous equation.

Construction of calibration curve:

Using standard stock solution of ROS, volume of, 1,2,3,4,5mL was taken to transfer into 10ml volumetric flask & the same procedure was followed for TEL, pipette out, 4,8,12,16,20 mL is volume transferred into 10ml volumetric flask & diluted to the mark with ACN & Milli Q-distilled water in the ratio (70:30) to get the concentration of each drugs. The solutions are scanned in UV range (200 nm - 400 nm). Maximum absorbance is shown at 242nm for ROS & 296 nm for TEL. The respective spectra represented in the (Figure 3,4).

Figure 3: Rosuvastatin at 242nm

Figure 4: Telmisartan 296nm

Preparation of working solution using marketed formulation :

Simultaneous estimation of ROS & TEL in Tablets. (Label claim 10 mg of ROS and 40 mg of TEL) Accurately weighed five tablets, calculated the average weight and was powdered which is equivalent to 1 mg of ROS & 4 mg of TEL. Transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask containing 100 ml of Solvent & was sonicated for 30 min dilution was made up to the mark with the same solvent. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper no. 41. An aliquot of 2 ml solution was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with the same solvent. It contains 2 g/ml of ROS and 8 g/ml of TEL. The absorbance is measured and calculations were performed by using simultaneous equations (Figure 5) and the results are tabulated in (Table 1).

Table 1 : Analysis Of Formulation

Drug	Amount		%Label Found	%RSD
	Label claim	Found		
ROS	10mg	9.5mg	95%	0.3
TEL	40mg	39.2mg	98%	0.39

Ros-Rosuvastatin, Tel -Telmisartan

* RSD of three Observations

Figure 5:overlain spectra of Formulation in ACN and water (70:30)

SIMULTANEOUS EQUATION METHOD:

To find both drugs at one time we use the equation method .TO measure how much X absorbs light at two wavelengths λ_1 and λ_2 .Let 's call the absorptivities A_{x1} ANS A_{x2} .Y absorbs light at these wavelengths too with absorptivities , a_{y1} and a_{y2} .where we dilute the samples and measure how light they absorb at λ_1 and λ_2 we get values A1 and A2 .The method helps the figure out the amounts of X and Y.

VALIDATION PARAMETERS FOR PROPOSED METHOD:

Linearity:

The test results obtained from this method is proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample.Italsoshowsthe analytes developed method used were within the linearity range. Thelinearity range found for ROS was 1-5g/ml at 242nm and 4-20g/ml for TEL at 296nm.The results and chromatogram seen are in (figure 6-9) (table 2).

Figure 6:Linearity graph ofROS AT 242nm

Figure 7:Linearity graph of ROS AT 296nm

Figure 8:Linearity graph of TEL AT 242nm

Figure 9: Linearity graph of TEL AT 296nm

LINEARITY TABULAR FOR BOTH DRUGS**Table 2 :Linearity table**

S.no	Parameters	ROS(results)	TEL(results)
1	λ_{max}	242nm	296nm
2	Linearity	1-5	4-20
3	Slope	0.0674	0.1599
4	r^2	0.9989	0.9972
5	Y intercept	0.006	0.0457

PRECISION

Precision-a measure of the reproducibility of the test, when the procedure is repeated on repetition of the same sample of homogenous material. Gives an indication of the existence of random errors and is represented by the relative standard deviation or coefficient of variation. The procedure used was to take the required concentration of 4, 8, 12 g/ml. The procedure was repeated for both the procedures, the results are displayed in (Table 3).

Table 3:Result of precision study of ROS and TEL

S.no	Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$		Absorbance				%RSD*			
	ROS	TEL	242nm		296nm		242nm		296nm	
			ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL
Intraday precision										
1	3	12	0.198	0.452	0.214	0.521	1.023	0.415	0.437	0.180
Interday precision										
1	3	12	0.201	0.458	0.216	0.524	0.465	0.206	0.439	0.179

*RSD of three observations

ROS-Rosuvastatin, TEL-Telmisartan

REPEATABILITY

Repeatability : It describes the degree of scatter between measurements made on identical test material under the same conditions over a short period of time. Repeatability was also called intra-assay precision. Result was shown in (Table 4)

Table 4: Repeatability results

S.no	Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$		Absorbance				%RSD			
			242nm		296nm		242nm		296nm	
	ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL	ROS	TEL
1	3	12	0.203	0.458	0.216	0.524	1.263	0.64	1.253	0.459

%RSD of Six determinations

RECOVERY STUDIES

For recovery studies both pure drug was taken and added in standard formulation in same volumetric flask. 5 mg of pure drug and 5 mg equivalent formulation was weighed and dissolved in a suitable solvent, sonicate for 20 mins. Later filter the solution take the required concentration and analyze in UV-Visible spectroscopy. From the absorbance we can calculate the drug recovered in formulation. Results were shown in (Table 5).

Table 5 :Results of recovery study

LEVEL	%Recovery	
	ROS	TEL
80%	96%	100%
100%	99%	101%
120%	100%	90%

LIMIT OF DETECTION AND QUANTIFICATION

The average of the standard deviation and the slope determined the limit of detection and limit of quantification. The LOD and LOQ was calculated from the linearity studies. These values are summarized in (Table 6).

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 * (\text{SD}/\text{Slope}) \text{ and } \text{LOQ} = 10 * (\text{SD}/\text{slope})$$

Table 6:Results of LOD &LOQ

Validation Parameters	ROS (1-5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	TEL(4-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)
LOD	0.508	1.4025
LOQ	1.54	4.25

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ROS and TEL was selected for analytical method development due to no method available for estimation of their combined assay from tablet formulation in the fixed dose, in present methods the solvent system like ACN and distilled water was used to estimate the studied drugs and completed validated and % recovery was calculated for three levels of 80 %, 100 % and 120 %, % recovery was 95.4-101.2%. In both the methods all validation parameters like precision, ruggedness, robustness, LOD, LOQ were determined, it was observed that % RSD values were less than 2 in above method. The developed method is accurate, economical, simple, rapid and suitable for quantification of ROS and TEL.

The methods are reliable and promising for the routine quality control of the drug substances. The proposed analytical method offer significant advantages to the reported UV and HPLC methods for simultaneous determination of ROS and TEL. Initially, it has low linearity range (1- 5g/mL for ROS and 4-20 g/mL for TEL) thus shows higher sensitivity than reported UV methods. Low %RSD shows high precision and reproducibility of the analysis and it is highly applicable for low dosage formulations. The concentration values obtained are less; hence usage of reagents also very less hence is an economical method.

CONCLUSION

The method described is simple, sensitive, specific and accurate for rapid determination of Rosuvastatin and Telmisartan in combined tablet dosage form and this methods may be successfully employed for their determination in combined dosage form in the control laboratories.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the management of PSG College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore for providing the facilities to carry out this research work

References

1. Shah BB, Patel BB, Gohil KN, Patel PM. Difference spectrophotometric method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Rosuvastatin calcium and Telmisartan in bulk and combined dosage form. *Int J Res Pharm Sci* 2012; 2(2):106-114.

2. Doshil N, Sheth A, Sharma A, Dave JB, Patel CN. Validated RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Rosuvastatin calcium and Telmisartan in pharmaceutical dosage form. *J Chem Pharm Res* 2010; 2(2):252-63.
3. Patel B, Seth A, Doshi N, Dave JB, Patel CN. Comparative in-vitro dissolution study of Rosuvastatin calcium and Telmisartan by RP-HPLC. *J Chem pharm res* 2010; 2(3):237-43.
4. Kotadia KS, Maheshwari DG. Chromatographic and spectrophotometric method for estimation of statin class drugs in bulk and in different dosage forms. *J Chem Pharm Res* 2015; 7(10):473-79.
5. Sharma S, Bhandari P. Simultaneous estimation of Rosuvastatin calcium and Fenofibrate in bulk and in tablet dosage form by UV-spectrophotometry and RP-HPLC. *J Pharm Res* 2012; 5 (4):2311-14.
6. Padmavathi M, Reshma MSR, Sindhuja YV, Nagaraju VK. Spectrophotometric methods for estimation of Telmisartan bulk drug and its dosage form. *Int J Res Pharm Chem* 2013; 3(2):320-25.
7. Ramadan AA, Mandil HH, Alsayed-ali R. Spectrophotometric determination of Rosuvastatin in pure form and pharmaceutical formulations through ion-pair complex formation using bromocresol green. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2015; 7(11):192-98.
8. Sevda RR, Ravetkar AS, Shirote PJ, UV Spectrophotometric estimation of Rosuvastatin calcium and Fenofibrate in bulk drug and dosage form using simultaneous equation method, *Int J ChemTech Res* 2011; 3(2):629-35.
9. Christian GD, Dasgupta PK, Schug KA. *Analytical Chemistry*, Seventh Edition, 2014 John Wiley & Sons.
10. "Indian Pharmacopoeia"1996. Volume.1, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, The Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad. Page no.144, 159
11. DrugBank. Rosuvastatin calcium [Internet]. [cited 2025 Apr 15]. Available from: <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB01098>
12. DrugBank. Telmisartan [Internet]. [cited 2025 Apr 15]. Available from: <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB00966>